

Search for Potential Anti-tumour Compounds. Part IX.

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A series of 5-pyrimidinyl-azo-benzene sulphonamides have been prepared with a view to test their antitumour activity.

5-ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINES have been found to possess folate reductase inhibitory and anticancer activity¹⁻⁴ and it is believed that the two activities are correlated. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to synthesise a series of compounds of the type (I), with a view to evaluate their anticancer activity.

(I)

The compounds were obtained by coupling diazotised sulpha drugs with substituted hydroxy, mercapto and amino pyrimidines at a suitable pH.

Experimental

The arylazopyrimidines were prepared by following one of the methods given below :

Method 'A' :

A solution of the appropriate sulpha drug (0.01 mole) in 90 ml. acetic acid (50%) or hydrochloric acid (3 ml.) and water (15 ml.) was rapidly cooled below 0° and diazotised by the addition of sodium nitrite (0.01 mole) in water (5 ml.) under vigorous stirring. After an hour, the diazonium salt was added to a cold stirred solution of the pyrimidine (0.01 mole) in dimethyl formamide (20 ml.) at 10°. The mixture was allowed to stand for 12 hr. at 0°; the pH during the reaction was maintained at 6. The dye which separated was then filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

Method 'B' :

Same as method 'A', except that the pyrimidine was dissolved in 10% sodium acetate solution instead of in dimethyl formamide. This crude product was dissolved in warm *N* NaOH, the solution filtered free of tarry or insoluble impurities and the product precipitated at pH 6 by the addition of acetic acid.

Method 'C' :

The diazonium salt prepared as above from the appropriate sulpha drug (0.01 mole) was added to a

TABLE I

R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.P.* °C	Method	Yield (%)	Molecular Formula	Analysis**		
								(%)	(%)	
1.	H	OH	CH ₃	OH	170(d)	A	64	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₅ SO ₄	C : 43.05 H : 3.33 N : 22.17	C : 42.71 H : 3.56 N : 22.65
2.	H	OH	CH ₃	SH	> 310	A	60	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₅ S ₂ O ₃	C : 41.18 H : 3.59 N : 21.12	C : 40.61 H : 3.38 N : 21.53
3.	H	NH ₂	OH	NH ₂	> 310	B	59	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₇ SO ₃	C : 38.26 H : 3.44 N : 31.25	C : 38.83 H : 3.56 N : 31.72

TABLE I (Contd)

R	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.P.* °C	Method	Yield (%)	Molecular Formula	Analysis**	
								Found (%)	Required (%)
4. 2-thiazolyl	NH ₂	OH	NH ₂	260(d)	B	70	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₈ S ₂ O ₃	N : 29.10	N : 28.56
5. guanidyl	NH ₂	OH	NH ₂	280(d)	B	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ N ₈ SO ₃	N : 35.75	N : 35.89
6. 2-pyrimidinyl	NH ₂	OH	NH ₂	302(d)	B	80	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ N ₈ SO ₃	N : 32.87	N : 32.55
7. 4,6-dimethyl-2-pyrimidinyl	NH ₂	OH	NH ₂	> 310	B	76	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₈ SO ₃	N : 30.76	N : 30.36
8. 2,6-dimethyl-4-pyrimidinyl	NH ₂	OH	NH ₂	> 310	B	76	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₈ SO ₃	N : 29.85	N : 30.36
9. 2-pyridyl	NH ₂	OH	NH ₂	> 310	B	72	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₈ SO ₃	N : 29.62	N : 29.01
10. H	OH	OH	NH ₂	> 310	C	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₈ SO ₄	C : 39.25 H : 3.90 N : 27.28	C : 38.71 H : 3.22 N : 27.09
11. 2-thiazolyl	OH	OH	NH ₂	> 310	C	82	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₇ S ₂ O ₄	N : 24.54	N : 24.91
12. guanidyl	OH	OH	NH ₂	290(d)	C	82	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₈ SO ₄	N : 32.07	N : 31.81
13. 2-pyrimidinyl	OH	OH	NH ₂	> 310	C	84	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₈ SO ₄	N : 29.05	N : 28.86
14. 4,6-dimethyl-2-pyridinyl	OH	OH	NH ₂	> 310	C	74	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₈ SO ₄	N : 27.26	N : 26.92
15. 2,6-dimethyl-4-pyrimidinyl	OH	OH	NH ₂	305(d)	C	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₈ SO ₄	N : 26.87	N : 26.92
16. 2-pyridyl	OH	OH	NH ₂	268(d)	C	76	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₇ SO ₄	N : 24.76	N : 25.06
17. H	OH	NH ₂	OH	> 310	B	72	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₈ SO ₄	C : 38.02 H : 3.54 N : 26.52	C : 38.71 H : 3.22 N : 27.09
18. 2-thiazolyl	OH	NH ₂	OH	> 310	B	74	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₇ S ₂ O ₄	N : 25.43	N : 24.91
19. guanidyl	OH	NH ₂	OH	> 310	B	74	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₈ SO ₄	N : 31.20	N : 28.86
20. 2-pyrimidinyl	OH	NH ₂	OH	303(d)	B	64	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ N ₈ SO ₄	N : 28.37	N : 28.86
21. 4,6-dimethyl-2-pyrimidinyl	OH	NH ₂	OH	> 310	B	68	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₈ SO ₄	N : 26.54	N : 26.92
22. 2,6-dimethyl-4-pyrimidinyl	OH	NH ₂	OH	> 310	B	69	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₈ SO ₄	N : 26.88	N : 26.92
23. 2-pyridyl	OH	NH ₂	OH	> 310	B	62	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₇ SO ₄	N : 25.12	N : 25.06

* All the m.p.s are uncorrected.

** For analyses the compounds were dried over phosphorus pentoxide at 110° for 16 hrs.

cold solution of pyrimidine (0.01 mole) in *N* NaOH (20 ml.). A bright yellow precipitate formed instantaneously; the resulting suspension was stirred for 15 min. The final pH was 6. The product was filtered, washed with cold water and was purified as in above method.

The m.p.s., yields and analyses of the different azo compounds are recorded in Table 1.

References

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